

Interview protocol for the paper “An Investigation of Low-Code Development Adoption in a Finnish Consulting Firm” by Dongmei Gao and Fabian Fagerholm.

Interview with LCD team lead

Format: online meeting with audio recording and transcription. (Meanwhile, use the phone to record)

Duration: 1 hour

Interview questions:

Part 1: Motivation

1. What terminology do you use to refer to low-code development on your team?
2. How do customers typically become low-code customers in your company?
 - a. How do you introduce the low-code solution to your customers?
3. Why has your company decided to offer low-code services to your customers? What benefits does the company see?
4. When do you decide to offer low-code to customers instead of something else?

Part 2: Work mode

The first question is important, so adjust the other questions according to the answer.

5. Could you describe a typical life-cycle of a low-code application? Does it differ in any way from an application developed using “traditional” agile?
6. Could you describe the overall process of how you communicate and collaborate with customers in low-code projects? Do you, as the head of the team, have any direct communication with customers?
7. What types of applications do you usually deliver to your customers?
 - a. (Listen for his initial explanation, then decide to ask follow-ups)
8. Since you work with two leading low-code development platforms, how do you decide which one to use to solve your customers' problems? (if developers decide this, we can leave this question when interviewing with developers)

Part 3: Governance structure

Participants might give some general answer, project managers and developers might be able to answer this in detail.

9. How do you maintain applications built on LCDPs after the first version is delivered? (Bug fixes, new features, ...)
 - a. Are customers responsible for further maintenance of the low-code applications or is the company responsible?

- b. What is the role of the customer's IT department in the maintenance?
- c. Do you use techniques similar to regular source code, like version control?
- 10. How do you operate applications built on LCDPs that you have delivered to customers? (Monitoring, keeping backends running, etc.)
 - a. What is the role of the customer's IT department in the operation?

Part 4: Low-code skills

- 11. When you recruit developers for the low-code team, what are the skill requirements? Do you recruit people who have only low-code development skills or are "traditional" professional developer skills required?
 - a. Do you have any ideas that can support and promote the career of employees in the team (low-code developers or pro-code developers)?
- 12. What kinds of skills and knowledge do your customers need when collaborating on a low-code project?

Part 5: Customer satisfaction

If time limits, we can leave this part of questions later

- 13. Have you ever collected customers' and/or end-users' feedback on the delivered low-code solution?
 - a. If yes: How do you collect the feedback?
- 14. Have you ever received any problem reports from your customers? What kind of problems?
- 15. What challenges do you typically experience during implementation?

Interview with team members

Format: online meeting with audio recording

Duration: 1 hour

Pre-interview questions:

1. Ask for the interviewee's consent (privacy notice and consent form are sent via email)
2. Which of these best describe your role? (developer, architect, designer or project manager)
3. Which platform do you most often work with? (OutSystems, Power Platform, or both)
4. How long have you been involved in low-code projects at the company?

Interview questions

Part 1: Background (5 mins)

1. Have you worked with low-code before the company's low-code team?
2. How did you get started with low-code in general?
3. How did you learn to use low-code?
4. What led you to the company's low-code team?
- a. Do you have experience working with traditional application development?

Part 2: Work mode (10-15 mins)

5. Can you shortly describe your role in your current project? What are your main responsibilities?
6. How do you collaborate with other different roles in the team?
 - a. How does the low-code platform affect your collaboration?
7. Could you describe a typical life-cycle of a low-code application? Start, continue, and end?
 - a. Since you work with two leading low-code development platforms, how do you decide which one to use to solve your customers' problems? (only for those involved in decision-making process)
 - b. Are there any differences in working with OutSystems compared to Pro-code design? (only for those have worked with both platforms)
 - c. How do you maintain applications built on LCDPs after the first version is delivered? (Bug fixes, new features, ...)

Part 3: Customer collaboration and communication (20 mins)

8. Could you describe the overall process of how you communicate and collaborate with customers in low-code projects?
 - a. Do you have any direct communication with customers?
 - b. Are there any differences compared to pro-code?
 - c. What are the roles of the people from the customer side that you are communicating with?

- d. What is the role of the customer's IT department in the development and operation?
- 9. Are there any challenges with customer communication and collaboration related to low-code?
- 10. What kinds of skills and knowledge do your customers need when collaborating on a low-code project?
- 11. Have you heard any doubts about low-code being expressed by customers?

Part 4: Overall experience and perception of low-code (20 mins)

- 12. How do you feel about working with low-code technology?
 - a. Have you experienced any challenges with low-code development?
- 13. What kinds of skills are important for developers working with low-code?
- 14. How about your personal preference? Do you see yourself continuing with low-code or are you interested in working more with pro-code applications?
- 15. What do you think about the future of low-code technology?
 - a. What do you think of the future of low-code in consulting?
- 16. Low-code is often mentioned together with citizen development – meaning that anyone can do development. What are your thoughts on this? Do you see any of that with your customers?

Thank you very much for your answers! Is there anything you think was left out or you want to add?